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Hire Purchase Law And Practice In Nigeria: A Historical Appraisal

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ABSTRACT

The origin and development of hire purchase law and practice in Nigeria is traceable to the English Law and Practice. In course of its application and operations, it has undergone significant changes since its inception during the colonial era. Commencing from its inception/introduction in Nigeria, hire Purchase agreements and practices drew extensively from the common law and doctrines of equity of England and the legal system in the United Kingdom. The evolution and introduction of hire purchase practice in Nigeria was aimed at improving the harsh economic system prevalent at the time and in order to promote and facilitate consumer purchases as well as encourage the consumers/hirer who does not have available funds but intends to buy or use costly cars and products to hire such goods for a monthly rent with the ultimate aim to purchase such goods after the payment of the agreed last installment. Therefore, this article examines the historical development and hire purchase law/agreements in Nigeria from its inception (the pre-independence era) to the post-independence period and further highlight the challenges facing parties involved in hire purchase agreement of this nature as well as recommendations to remedy the bad effects of the current hire purchase law in Nigeria.

Keywords: Hire Purchase Law, Hire Purchase Practice, Nigeria

1. INTRODUCTION

Hire Purchase agreement can simply be understood as an agreement where the owner of goods transfers possession of the goods to another person called the hirer for an agreed periodical or installmental payments. Ultimately, the hirer has an option to either buy or return the goods, subject of the agreement. This type of transactions/agreement enables the hirer an opportunity to buy expensive products which ordinarily he could not afford to buy it and instantly pay the whole cost price enbloc, before title to the goods can be transferred to him. In course of the work, it was discovered that hire purchase agreement in most cases occasions hardship to the hirer as a few of the hire purchase agreement end in discord.

The owner of the goods/property usually take undue advantage of the unequal position of the hirer, by the owner terminating the agreement when the hirer has substantially paid or performed his own part of the hire purchase agreement. The article ends with a call or recommendation of the serious concern posed to the hirer by certain provisions of the 2004 Act, in favour of the owner of the goods/products.

2. DEFINITION OF CONCEPTS/TERMS

For purpose of clarity, it is imperative to define certain concepts

i. HIRE PURCHASE

The term hire purchase is defined by the *Hire Purchase Act*,¹ as the bailment of goods pursuant to an agreement, where the Bailee may eventually buy the goods and the property in the goods will pass to the

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Bailee. Therefore, hire purchase agreement shall be constructed accordingly and if by virtue of two or more agreements none constitutes a hire purchase agreement, there is a bailment of goods. And in the circumstance, either the Bailee may buy the goods, or the property may pass to the bailee. Where this happens, the agreement shall be treated for the purpose of the Act, as a single agreement made at the time the last agreement was made.² Hire Purchase law constitutes an agreement where the owner of goods agrees to hire his goods to a hirer with the option that the hirer will be able to purchase the goods at the payment of the last instalment/end of the agreement³. Further, it is a legal agreement made in writing and signed by the parties to the agreement, and becomes binding on the parties to the agreement.

ii. **BAILEE**

According to Black's Law Dictionary⁴, a Bailee is: A person who receives personal property from another and has possession of goods or personal property but not ownership of the goods or personal property⁵. The responsibilities of Bailee includes taking reasonable care of the goods in his procession during the pendency of the hire and returning the property as received with legal liabilities and damages (if not finally purchased by the Bailee) hirer's obligation to take reasonable care of the goods is independent of the owner's duty to give quit possession of the goods to the hirer.⁶ From the definitions, it is clear that bailee is a common law term, which involves change of possession of goods/property without change in ownership. Examples are, when an individual or group of people deliver their telephone, watches, wall clock, motor cycle, motor car etc to the repairer/mechanic or electrician for repairs⁷, which involves a day-to-day activities between the two parties, namely: the Bailee and the bailor.

An agreement of Hire Purchase can simply be understood as an agreement whereby the owner of the goods transfers possession to another person called the hirer for an agreed periodical payment which at the end, the hirer has the option to either buy or return the goods.⁸ Conversely, it can be said that it is an arrangement whereby the buyer buys expensive consumer or other goods and the buyer makes an initial down payment and pays the balance later together with the interests in instalments. This happens when the buyers cannot pay the agreed price for an item or goods in a lump sum and is the goods are delivered by the owner to the hirer on credit with an initial deposit or not and take custody of the goods, on deposit on a monthly basis or rent. From the definitions above, it appears that for a transaction to qualify as a hire purchase, it must be that the owner of the goods transfers possession of the goods to another person while he retains the title/ownership in the goods.⁹

iii. **BAILMENT**

Bailment of goods involves the temporary transfer of possession of goods or assets from one person to another, who are the bailor and the bailee respectively¹⁰ Bailments is fiduciary in nature and creates a type

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¹ Cap H4 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004, Section 20(1)

² *Ibid*, Section 20(1)

³ Available online @<https://www.ajetlawyer.com-law-hire-purchase-nigeria>, accessed 20/1/2026

⁴ B. A. Garaer, 9th edition, 141 cited in Olanrewaju Olamide, the Law of Hire Purchase in Nigeria; available online @www.djetlawyer.com accessed 18/2/2026; 8th edition of black's law dictionary P.151 bailee is defined as a person who receives personal property from another person as a bailment. And bailment is defined as a delivery of personal property by one person (the bailor) to another (the bailee) who holds the property from a certain purpose under an express or implied in fact contract. Unlike a gift of personal property, a bailment involves a charge in possession but not in title in the

⁵ Will Kenton, what is a bailee? Definition, key roles and everyday examples? Available onle @www.investopedia.com, accessed 18/2/2026.

⁶ N. A. Vincent, The meaning, Evolution and Essence of Hirer Purchase; Available online @www.vinelegal.com.ng accessed 8/2/2026.

⁷ *Ibid*

⁸ *Ibid*; *Aro v Joe Allen & Co Ltd (1979) 2 FNR 292 at 295 per Okagbue JCA*

⁹ *Afrotec Technical Service Nig. Ltd V. MIA & Sons Ltd & Anor (2000) 15 NWLR (Pt. 692) 730, SC.*

¹⁰ N. H. Worluh-Okolie *et al*, contract of bailment in Nigeria: An Appraisal in Fountain University Law Journal, (2024) vol. No.1, available online @www.fountainjournals.com, accessed 06/3/2026

of bailment recognized in contract of bailment which are: (a) gratuitous bailment. For example, when one lend an item or car to a friend(b), Bailment for reward, which is when both parties benefits from the act of bailment,¹¹ For example, when one parks a car in a car park and payment is made. Other types of bailment are finder of lost items, (who must take care of the item and Pawn (pledge) which involves delivery of goods as a security for a debt. According to Worlu-Okolie and Igbinoso-Okoro,¹² bailment is traced to a French word 'bailer' which means to deliver. This involves the delivery of goods from one person to another and subsequent redelivery of the goods to the bailor in accordance with the bailors instrument. The goods remain with the bailor and the goods does not pass to the bailee except under an ordinary hire purchase contract where the parties may intend that Property in the goods should pass.

3. NATURE OF HIRE PURCHASE

The true nature of hire purchase is determined from the terms of the agreement and the court seised with case of this nature should construe it accordingly, unless it is prohibited by statute. This can be discovered if of the Court goes behind the document to determine the true nature of the transactions. Where the purchaser desirous to purchase the goods, but does not have sufficient money for the purchase, borrows the amount from a third party and pays it to the vendor; the character of the transaction between the customer and the third party is a loan transaction. To be a valid hire purchase agreement, such transactions must be in writing and signed by both parties clearly specifying the ingredients of a valid hire purchase which includes but not limited to:

- a) There must be a clear description of the goods;
- b) It must state the cash price of the goods;
- c) The hire purchaser price, which is the total sum that must be paid to the hirer and/or to purchase the goods at the last instalmental payment;
- d) The deposit;
- e) The duration of the hire and/or the time to complete payment and own the goods
- f) The monthly instalments. However, the law of some States of the federation required that the applicable interest rate should be disclosed into the agreement of parties and regulates the interest and charges applicable to the agreements
- g) A reasonable and comprehensive statement of the parties' rights as well as right to cancel the agreement during the cooling-off period
- h) The right of the hirer to determine the contract when he feels like doing so with a justifiable reason(s)¹³

4. CHARACTERISTICS OF A HIRE PURCHASE AGREEMENT UNDER THE COMMON LAW

In order to know whether a transaction is a hire purchase or not; certain basic elements must be present in the agreement of parties.

First, the hirer has no right to redeem the hired goods, if he has not completed the payment of all the agreed instalments. Similarly, it is also applicable, if he the hirer has paid all previous instalments punctually but he was a day late in paying the last installment. In *Benthworth Finance Nig Ltd v De Bank Transport Ltd*,¹⁴ where the Court held that the provision for punctual payment meant that the instalments must be paid on the stipulated date. A one day delay in the payment could be regarded as a breach of the agreement entitling the owner to retrieve the goods. This is regardless of the fact that it was the last installment that was delayed.

¹¹ N. H Worlu-Okolie and A B Igbinosa-Okoro, An Appraisal, Ibid

¹² N H, Worlu-Okolie and A B Igbinosa-An Appraisal of the Nature and Scope of contract of bailment in Nigeria, in international journal, in International Journal of Academic Pedagogical research, 2024 vol. 8, issue 2, available online@www.ijeaisorg/Ijapr, accessed 06/3/2026.

¹³ Will Kenton(n.5); (n3)

¹⁴ (1968) 3 ALLNLR 52

Second, the agreement does not transfer property or proprietary interest in the goods to the hirer.¹⁵ What the hirer has is possession but if he has an option to own and paid all the instalments. In *Amusa and Anor. V. Benthworth Finance Nig. Ltd.*¹⁶ The Court held *inter alia*, that where the hirer exercises his option to terminate the hire purchase agreement he cannot complain that the minimum payment clause is a penalty.

Third, when the owner seizes the goods and he decides to sell it to another party, he (the owner) is not accountable to the hirer, even if there was just one instalmental payment remaining. From the above decision, no right accrues to the owner even though the hirer has paid a substantial part of the amount of the goods agreed. In the case of *Atere v Amao*,¹⁷ where a motor lorry was on hire purchase agreement, the total price payable was £1000 but the hirer had paid £995 remaining £5 for the last installment which he defaulted when the owner took the lorry from the hirer and repossessed it. The court held the seizure was lawful.

Fourth, copies of the signed hire purchase agreement, where not usually given to the hirer.

Fifth, the absence of statutory regulations created room for a lot of sharp practices and occasioned hardship on the hirer. This allowed the owner of the goods to charge exorbitant interest rate against the hirer.

Sixth, according to Agashi¹⁸ whenever the hirer defaults in payment (unless agreed by the parties in the hire purchase agreement) no note for the termination may be required when there is default. In Nigeria, the common law rules and practices, relating to hire purchase agreement were operational but with the enactment the first, English hire purchase Act in 1938 which was also applicable in Nigeria during the colonial period as well as the subsequent enactment of Nigeria hire purchase Act 1965 most of the harsh rules and practices against the hirer prevalent under the common law rules, were ineffective and changed. During the period when a purchase agreements became regulated by statutes, the character of hirer purchase practices and agreements changed in favour of the hirer contrary to the common law rules; though certain basis features of hire purchase agreement were retained by the statute.

5. SOURCES AND HISTORICAL APPRAISAL OF HIRE PURCHASE LAW/ PRACTICE IN NIGERIA

The law on hire purchase is of recent origin in English law. Before the enactment of the first statute on hire purchase in England in 1938- (hire purchase Act 1938), common law rules applied to hire purchase transactions. Historically, hire purchase is foreign to the customary and indigenous system of law in Nigeria. The history of Nigeria hire purchase is part of the history of the received English law, which has become incorporated into Nigerian legal system; and consequently part of our laws. There are five phases (periods) in the commencement/ development of hire purchase law in Nigeria. It spans from the common law era, which is the Pre- 1938 era; Pre-1965 era; 1965 Act era; the Application and expansion era; Amendments and regulation era and the modernization period, that is Hire Purchase Act LFN 2004.

During the period before 1965, there were no local laws or rules of practice regulating the practice and operations of hire purchase transactions¹⁹ however, local traders sold goods on credit and consequently, foreign bodies, organizations and business carried along their foreign statutes like common law of England, doctrines of equity and 1938 hire purchase Act, in Nigeria. In the period after 1938, Nigeria effectively had one main statutory hire purchase law, which is the hire purchase Act 1965, alongside prior common-law rules and doctrines of equity. The legislation currently in operation is the Hire Purchase Act 1965 now Cap H4 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004. In this section, this paper will discuss some key facts and the sources of legislations on hire purchase in Nigeria.

¹⁵ N. A. Vincent! The meaning, evolution and Essence of Hire Purchase available online @www.vinelegal. com.ng; accessed 8/2/2026

¹⁶ (1966) NMLR 275; (1957) NNLR 176

¹⁷ *Atere v Amao* (1957) NENLR 176

¹⁸ A M Agashi, An Analysis of the hire purchase contract

¹⁹ Nathan Ibrahim, *et al*; Examining the Nigerian Hire Purchase Act: Addressing monetary limitations and imbalance in legal protection to enhance commercial Development, in Nexus University journal of legal studies, 2025, 11(1) 5-15, available on line @https.www.riujournals.ok.uk, accessed 10/3/2026

i. Hire Purchase Act 1938²⁰ The concept of hire purchase is an important aspect of commercial law and commercial transactions. The first English Hire Purchase Act was in 1938. Ibrahim, *et al* have argued that the modern hire purchase agreement originated in the mid-Victorian custom in furniture trade whereby people/customers who were unable to pay for the furniture at the desired time and without sufficient funds were allowed to take them²¹ Hire Purchase Act 1938 being the first United Kingdom's big consumer-protection step to hire purchase agreements, certain provisions of the Act protected trade and commercial relationships to the effect that before signing the agreement, the owner must give the hirer a written statement of the cash price; hire purchase price, deposit and instalmental payments schedule. Another mutual benefits to the hirer and the owner as contained in the Act, is the restriction on repossession of the goods by the owner if the hirer did not pay a particular instalment at all or delayed in the repayment. Here once the hirer has paid one-third of the price for goods other than motor vehicle which is half of the contract amount, the owner cannot take back (*sntach-back*) possession of the goods from the hirer except through the order of the court.

Other provisions of the Act, which brought about transparency; is the provision for implied warranty relating to warranty of quit possession; owners warranty that goods are free from third party rights/charges; warranty of merchantability (satisfactory) of products; the owner should supply goods that are fit for the purpose; the owner warrants to deliver contract goods that must correspond with sample or description or goods agreed by reference, among others.²² Thus for the first time, there was mutuality of fairness and transparency in hire purchase transactions to both parties to the contract. The former common law harsh rules which encouraged sharp practices and in equitable applications against the hirer and in favour of the owner as contained in the court decision in *Benthworth Finance Nig. Ltd v De Bank Transported Ltd*²³ were remedied. The first judicial approval to contract of hire purchase was given by the House of Lords in the case of *Helby v Matthews*.²⁴ In that case, Helby, was a dealer who delivered a Piano to Brewster on terms that Brewster would pay a monthly rent of 10 shillings and 6 pence, as well as after 36 payments, the Piano would become the property of Brewster. Meanwhile, the property in the goods (piano) remained with Helby. There was a condition that Brewster can terminate the contract at any time or day returning the piano to Helby and stop payment of the instalments. After a few payments, Brewster pledged the piano to Mr. Matthew a third party, who took the piano in good faith and without notice of Helby's rights. Helby sued to recover the piano from Matthew and the question before the Court for determination was whether the 3rd party (Matthew) has a good title to the piano. The House of Lords unanimously held that the action to recover the Piano succeeded as the court decided that the agreement between Helby and Brewster is not an agreement for Brewster to buy within section.²⁵ Factors Act 1889. All that he (Brewster) undertook to do was to make monthly payments in installments, although he had the option to buy the piano if he had exercised that option, he could have become the purchaser of the piano instead of the hirer.

ii. HIRE PURCHASE ACT 1965

This is the first Nigerian indigenous law on hire purchase agreements and credit sales transactions. The 1965 Nigerian Act was essentially modelled after and basically took the UK's Hire Purchase Act 1938; but was modified and reflected to suit local use. The Act was made to apply throughout Nigeria in 1968. While the original Act 1965 was initially operational in the Federal Capital territory Lagos State only.

- However, by virtue of Hire Purchase (Application and Expansion) Decree²⁶ it became applicable throughout Nigeria; but at finally and fully came into force on 1st October, 1968²⁷ The Hire

²⁰ Cap 53. this applies to all hire purchase and credit sales

²¹ Ibid, available online@www.lexo.co.uk/vid/hire-purchase-act-1938, accessed 103/2026

²² Hire Purchase Act, Ibid, sections 1 and 2

²³ (n.14) 52

²⁴ (1895) AC 471, HL

²⁵ Section 9 factors Act 1889

²⁶ Decree No 42, 1966; Eko Solicitors, Hirer Purchase in Nigeria: Your Ultimate Guide to Ownership, available online@www.ekosolicitors.com accessed 8/3/2026.

²⁷ This is by virtue of Hire Purchase (Amendment Decree No. 23, 1970)

Purchase (Amendment Decree 1970) made certain changes to sections 8 and 9 of the Hire Purchase Act 1965. The changes relate to the hirer's right to terminate the Hire purchase agreement as well as the restrictions on repossession of the goods by the owner.

The Act also made provisions for the protection of the hirer's interest. Some of the ways it protected the hirer are:

- (a) It provides for the full involvement of the hirer in the formation of the transactions;
- (b) It restricted the owners' contracted freedom by inserting some implied terms²⁸, like warranty that the goods are fit for purpose,²⁹ the hirer should have quiet possession of the goods; the goods delivered should be of merchantable (satisfactory) quality;
- (c) The goods delivered must correspond with the sample or with the description or reference to the sample during the period of the hire; the owner must maintain and deliver goods in a good state as they were at the time the agreement was made.³⁰ It also prohibits the implementation of some terms detrimental to the hirer
- (d) The hirer is entitled to demand and have a copy of the hire purchase agreement
- (e) The hire purchase agreement must state the list of goods, the hire purchase price and a statement of the cash price, the deposit paid, amount of the instalment and dates they are payable.³¹
- (f) The Act grants the hirer the right to terminate the agreement while also limiting the liability that he would incur as a consequence of the termination.
- (g) It restricts the owner of the goods from repossessing the goods indiscriminately³². The owner can only repossess the goods when the hirer has defaulted in payment or in breach of the agreement and through an order of court.
- (h) It nullifies attempt by the owner to exclude the implied terms and conditions. The objects and reasons for the Hire Purchase Act and credit sales transactions is to reduce the harsh and oppressive rules and practices against the hirer by the owner under the common law rules/practices. The classes of goods covered by the Act as contained in section 1 of the act are:-
 - a. Every hire purchase deal which total cost is less than two thousand naira and
 - b. Any and all agreements pertaining to cars and other vehicles³³. Thus other goods which are not covered by the provisions of the Act are governed by common law rules and doctrines of equity in Nigeria.³⁴ Even though the Hire Purchase law regulates hire purchase transactions the rule of common law and doctrines of equity are simultaneously applied where no provisions are provided in the Act.

By virtue of Application and expansion law, the Hire Purchase Act of 1965 in Nigeria became effective on 1st October, 1968 and applied and became operational throughout Nigeria two years later after the Act became applicable operational.³⁵ There were minor amendments made in two sections, that is sections 8³⁶ and 9³⁷ of the Hire Purchase (Amendment Decree No 23) 1970.

The minor amendment to section 8 of the principal Act 1965, is to the effect that section 8 included and spelt out what happens when the hirer exercises the right to terminate the agreement by adding the

²⁸ (n.22) Eko Solicitors

²⁹ Section 4(2)

³⁰ (n.10); see also section 4(1) of the Act

³¹ Hire purchase Act 1965, Section 2(1)(b)

³² Section 3(b) of the Act

³³ Ibid, section 20 defines motor vehicle as a mechanical propelled vehicle intended for or adapted for use on road or for agricultural purposes.

³⁴ Eko Solicitors (n.22)

³⁵ C. J. Okoye the hire purchase contract available globallaw.com.access

³⁶ A hirer shall at any time before the final payment under the hire purchase agreement falls due, be entitled to determine the agreement by giving notice of termination, in writing to any person entitled or authorized to receive any sums payable under the agreement and shall on determining the agreement be liable, without prejudice to any liability which has accrued before the termination to pay the amount if any, which one half of the hire purchase price exceeds the total sum paid and the sum due for the hire purchase price immediately before the termination or such less amount as may be specified in the agreement.

³⁷ section 9 of the Act

requirement that the hirer must immediately return the goods and settle any outstanding liability (damages) for failure to take reasonable care. It also clarified the wording of the notice and payment formula. This was not explicit in the 1965 Act. Moreover, all hire purchase agreements involving motor vehicles are covered despite the price.

Further, minor provision contained in the amendment Decrees No 23, 1970, is that where a hirer has paid at least one-third of the total hire purchase price, the owner cannot responses the goods without a valid court order.

iii. HIRE PURCHASE ACT CAP H4 LFN 2004

The Hire Purchase Act 2004, is a re-enactment of 1990 Act while the 1990³⁸ was substantially modelled after the amended Decree No 23 1970, and same was incorporated in the 2004 Act.³⁹ This 2004 Act addressed minor operational charges relating to sections 8 and 9 of the 1965 principal Act, 2004 which refined and consolidated the Act thus:

- a. there is statutory restriction on repossession of goods subject of the hire purchase agreement. In section 11 of the 2004 consolidated Act it is stipulated that after the hirer has paid up to 50% (fifty percent) of the agreed monetary payment to the owner, the owner is restricted from re-possessing the goods through self-help or impunity or without notice to the hirer, except through due process of an action in the court whereby the hirer will be put on notice and there is a valid order of court.
Though, the 1965 Act prohibited repossession of goods by the owner but there was no provision in the Act that provided that for the owner to repossess the goods, there must be valid court order, after an action is instituted in the law court. Consequently, the 2004 Act expanded the protection accorded the hirer in this regard.
- b. Requirement for the termination of contract section 8 of the hire purchase Act 2004, is a right of the hirer to terminate the contract, return the contract goods and/or pay damages. Though the 2004 Act retained this but spelt out consequences of this action by the hirer etc.
- c. Restriction about advertisements the 2004 Act controls misleading advertising and places consequences for misleading adverts. In the 1965 Act, there is no specific provisions expressly stating the consequences of misleading adverts.
- d. Definition and what constitutes requirement of hire purchase. In section 1 of the 1965 Act, the hire purchase agreement focuses on agreements where possession passes only but ownership does not pass to the hirer, except after paying all the instalments. However, the 2004 Act broadens and clarified this features of hire purchase to include agreements where the hirer may buy the goods for a nominal consideration not based on the payment of all the installments.
- e. Agreements void for non-compliance with contractual implied terms. Section 3 of the 2004 Act, provides for six types of harsh terms or conditions if contained in the hire purchase agreement of parties, are void for non-compliance.

The six types are (a)where the agreement gives power to the party to terminate agreement for breach of a minor term that is unrelated to payments, such termination is void. Any term in the agreement allowing the owner power to seize the goods subject of the agreement, without court order is void, if the hirer has paid more than 50% (fifty percent) or more than half of the total contract prices (c)such term is void where the agreement allows the owner to increase price of the hire purchase, for been harsh and arbitrary. (d)No power for waiver of rights any if the agreement provides that party can waive his statutory rights in the agreement of this nature it is void. (e) similarly, if any term in the agreement of parties allows for right to assign or terminate their right is void and (f)where any term of the agreement allow a party to enter any premises with force to seize goods such stipulation is void, because no party has the right to agree on terms outside the express provisions of the statute.

³⁸ Cap 160 laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 1990

³⁹ A.M Agadi (n.16)

- f. The contents of the agreement was under the 2004 Act though the 1965 Act require for a written memorandum stating the price the hire purchase price and each installmental payment to be specified; however, the provisions of section 4 of the 2004 Act provides for the same provisions but added that information regarding these facts must be specific.
- iv. Issues and deficiencies of the hire purchase Act 2004 considered while the 2004 hire purchase Act is applauded for making noticeable changes to bring into practice fairness to the hirer and respite to the owner relating to termination; there are noticeable and inherent challenges and deficiencies of the 2004 Act. These issues and deficiencies will be discussed in this section of the paper.
- a) There is still ambiguities in repossession right of the owner against the hirer. The provisions of sections 8 – 10 and section 14 of the Act are still complex and in unfair in application, according to chukwu⁴⁰
 - b) Secondly, the Act lack provision for the protection of an innocent third party who are not subject to hire purchase agreement but bought goods from the hirer. ⁴¹ Invariably, it is an over protection of the hirer. ⁴²
 - c) Third, the act still retains penalty and fines that are outdated and out of tune with the modern times, inflation and current economic realities. ⁴³
 - d) Fourth, the Act lacks provisions on digital and technological advancement. The world is moving in a speed of light and adoption of digital application and practices, appears ease the way of doing hire purchase business in Nigeria.

6. Conclusion

Hire purchase agreement bridges the gap between aspirations and ownership in Nigeria.⁴⁴ It offers vital access to goods despite the high cost which ordinarily cannot be afforded by the people/consumers and other challenges in the system. Although, the Act purports to balance the rights, obligations and liabilities of the hirer and the owner as well as protecting the consumers of the product; it has in several ways raised concerns and challenges. The Act similarly appears to be in tandem with the global best practices, as it integrates several legal reforms/innovations lacking under the common law rules/practices as well as in the hire purchase Act 1965. This innovations in the 2004 Act, is capable of improving the economy, creating peace of mind to the hirer and the owner as well as creating employment to teeming unemployed youth and members of the public in Nigeria.

However, it should be noted that even though some of these provisions of 2004 Act have been tested and decided upon in the courts of law, and the extent of its applicability to contemporary issues reasonably determined, there are obvious concerns and challenges posed by the Act to both the hirer and the owner; making the consumers of goods under hire purchase agreement skeptical of the potency of the provisions of the new Act. Thus, in order to boost further and strengthen the application of hire purchase agreement and the 2004 hire purchase Act.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are proffered:

- (a) There should be an amendment of section 1 of the Act, to increase the monetary limits of all category of goods covered by the Act as well as motor vehicle transactions, in order to meet the

⁴⁰ O J Chukwu, 'Balancing owners' Right and Hirer's protection: A study of section 14 of the hire purchase Act and its implications on hire purchase agreement in journal of commercial and property law unzik avalabel@online@www.journale.unizik.edu.ngaccessed 10/3/2020

⁴¹ Hire Purchase Act cap H4 LFN 2004, Section 9; Victoria Agbakwuru, 'A critique of the hire purchase Act and an examination of its continued relevance in the 21st century transactions, Available on line @ www.researchgate.net, accessed 20th March, 2026

⁴² *Ibid*, section 9 which also provides that the owner wrongfully repossess goods from the hirer, the hirer can recover all the installments paid to the owner, this is an over protection of the hirer. In as much as the Act intense to protect the hirer from the capricious hands of the owner, that should have being mutuality of fairness to both.

⁴³ *Ibid*, section 1 (a)

⁴⁴ Ojienoh Segun Justice, 'hire purchase in Nigeria: Your ultimate guide to ownership' available on line @ www.ekosolicitors.com,accessed 20th March, 2026.

current realities and inflationary trends. Such review will raise the compliance and obedience to the law by the parties to the agreement.

- (b) An amendment to section 9 of the Act, to provide for mutuality of fairness to both the hirer and the owner. A third party who buys or transacts with the hirer but does not know the agreement reached between the hirer and the owner, should not be made to suffer especially when the content of the agreement was not brought to his notice.
- (c) The provision for digital transactions in a hire purchase agreement like electronic signature, virtual negotiations, agreement of parties sent electronically and transfer/receipt of hire purchase agreement done electronically; will not only ease the way of doing hire purchase business but will eliminate tardiness and other noticeable inconveniences in doing it manually.
- (d) The penalties and fines sections of the Act, should to be increased to boost the morale and reliance on parties' agreement.
- (e) The Act should be amended to make it autotomous/indigenous by including classes of goods and practices in our local circumstances.